

CONDUCTING SOCIAL-PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITIES WITH ADOLESCENTS WHO
CONSUME ALCOHOLIC BEVERAGES

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the issue of organizing socio-pedagogical activities with adolescents who consume alcohol. Adolescence is an important stage in the formation of a person, and the use of alcohol can lead to social, psychological and pedagogical problems. The article analyzes the causes of alcohol consumption, its impact on the development of adolescents, and the tasks of a social pedagogue in combating this problem. The authors highlight social-pedagogical approaches, effective methods of psychological and preventive work, and emphasize the importance of cooperation with educational institutions, families and the public.

Keywords: adolescents, alcohol, social pedagogy, prevention, rehabilitation, psychological support, social adaptation, upbringing, risk group, pedagogical approach.

Adolescence is an important stage in human life, during which the formation of the personality, adaptation to the environment and the ability to make independent decisions develop. However, children of this age, under the influence of psychological, social and family factors, may be prone to various harmful habits, including alcohol consumption. This article aims to consider the role of social pedagogy in working with adolescents who drink alcohol, analyze the causes of the problem and consider preventive measures.

Various factors can cause adolescents to drink alcohol.

Family factors: Parents' alcohol consumption, family conflicts and neglect have a negative impact on adolescents.

Social environment: Trying alcohol among friends can occur as a result of social pressure.

Psychological factors: Problems such as stress, depression, and low self-esteem can push adolescents into harmful habits.

Influence of mass media: Positive portrayal of alcohol products in advertisements and films also affects the minds of adolescents.

Children's addiction to alcohol and its consequences Children's addiction to alcohol occurs mainly in three stages: early childhood, preschool and primary school age, and adolescence and young adulthood. Although the effect of alcohol on the physical and mental development of a child at each stage is different, the common point is that this process can ultimately lead to serious negative consequences.

1. Early childhood (0-3 years) During this period, children do not consume alcohol voluntarily, but if their mother drank alcohol during pregnancy or breastfeeding, this negatively affects the child's development. Alcohol consumed during pregnancy can damage the child's central nervous system, causing problems such as physical and mental developmental anomalies, epilepsy, and mental retardation.

2. Preschool and primary school age (3-9 years old) During this period, children may become interested in alcohol under the influence of the environment. The lack of pedagogical knowledge of

parents and the acceptance of alcohol consumption in the family as a normal state of affairs can arouse interest in alcohol in the child. As a result, the likelihood of trying alcohol from a young age increases, which may lead to the risk of poisoning the body.

3. Adolescence and adolescence (9-18 years old) At this stage, adolescents may become addicted to alcohol under the influence of the family environment, the environment, and the media. Adolescents who do not have sufficient knowledge about the harmful effects of alcoholism may try alcohol as a result of stress, family problems, or not knowing how to fill their free time.

Social pedagogical work with adolescents who consume alcohol

1. Prevention of the causes and consequences of alcoholism. This should be done by holding discussions on topics related to alcoholism. All participants in the group must follow these discussions.

2. Organization of adolescents' free time, because in order to spend free time meaningfully, it is necessary to establish sections, clubs, and children's and youth organizations.

3. Anti-alcohol education conducted by a social pedagogue should be aimed at forming independent views of children.

4. The school pedagogical team should organize an anti-alcohol committee.

The issue of socio-pedagogical activities with adolescents who consume alcohol is one of the current areas in the field of social pedagogy. This process includes the following main areas:

1. Identifying the roots of the problem

The social pedagogue should first study the reasons for the adolescent's alcohol consumption. This may be due to the following: Problems in the family environment (neglect, family conflicts, parents who consume alcohol). Negative influence of friends and the environment. Psychological problems (feeling lonely, depression, anxiety) Inability to effectively organize free time.

2. Prevention and early intervention

Partnership with the family: Conducting conversations with parents, increasing their responsibility. School and neighborhood cooperation: Conducting seminars and conversations among students about the harms of alcohol. Psychological support: Providing advice to the teenager based on an individual approach. Involvement in sports and creative circles: Helping the teenager give up alcohol by effectively organizing his free time.

3. Rehabilitation and social adaptation

Involvement in social support programs: Cooperating with social service centers. Organizing meetings and group therapy: Increasing motivation among teenagers through mutual influence. Involvement in labor activities: Directing teenagers to vocational training.

4. Legal education

Providing legal information about the harmful effects of alcohol. Strengthening educational work on the consequences of alcoholism. Cooperation with law enforcement agencies to prevent crimes.

Adolescence (11-14 years old)

During adolescence, children learn to make independent decisions. Therefore, the task of a social educator is to involve children in a healthy environment and prevent them from making wrong decisions. A social educator does this using the following methods:

1. Eliminating factors that negatively affect the child's life.

2. Social education of the person, individual consultations.

3. Providing children with moral and normative knowledge in order to prevent crimes.

4. Explaining to adolescents the social norms of society and using auxiliary methods. A great example is needed in society

Today, alcohol consumption among young people is one of the most pressing problems. Various factors can cause adolescents to become addicted to this harmful habit: family problems, the wrong friendship environment, psychological pressure, indifference or insufficient attention. Fighting this problem places a great responsibility not only on parents, but also on educators, psychologists and other members of society.

Causes of the problem: Adolescence is one of the most important stages in a person's life, during which they try to make independent decisions and determine how they will behave in society. Alcohol consumption is often caused by: Problems in the family environment (disagreements, neglect, improper upbringing); Influence of friends and social pressure; Lack of meaningful organization of free time; Direct or indirect promotion of advertising and the media; Psychological problems and the desire to express oneself. Tasks of a social pedagogue: To discourage adolescents from drinking alcohol, a social pedagogue should work in the following main areas:

1. Preventive explanatory work - Providing adolescents with a detailed explanation of the harmful effects of alcohol, promoting a healthy lifestyle.
2. Meaningful organization of free time - Keeping them busy with useful activities by involving them in sports, art, science clubs, cultural events and group activities.
3. Psychological and pedagogical support - Understanding the personal problems of adolescents, providing them with individual assistance, and increasing their self-confidence.
4. Working with parents - Involving parents in educational processes, communicating with them regularly, and providing advice on improving the family environment.
5. Creating a friendly environment - Directing adolescents to communicate with peers who think positively and are not indifferent to their future. Important aspects of working with adolescents who drink alcohol To reduce alcohol consumption among adolescents and prevent this harmful habit, social educators should use the following approaches:

3. Anti-alcohol education conducted by a social pedagogue should be aimed at forming independent views of children.
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